

Complexes of Tin Tetrahalides with Some Aromatic Amine N-oxides

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Ten hitherto unknown complexes of SnX_4 ($\text{X}=\text{Cl}$, Br or I) with picoline N-oxide, quinoline N-oxide, isoquinoline N-oxide and 2, 2'-bipyridyl N, N'-dioxide have been synthesised and characterised through elemental analysis, molecular weight and conductance data. On the basis of IR spectral studies probable geometry for the complexes is proposed.

NUMEROUS coordination compounds of aromatic amine N-oxides with a wide variety of metal salts have been prepared and characterised¹. There are also reports on adducts of some of these ligands such as pyridine N-oxide and 2,4-substituted pyridine N-oxides with tin tetrahalides²⁻⁷. In this communication we describe some hitherto unknown complexes of picoline N-oxide (PicO), quinoline N-oxide (QO), isoquinoline N-oxide (IsqO) and 2,2'-bipyridyl N,N'-dioxide (BipyO₂) with tin tetrahalides.

Experimental

Tin tetrachloride, -tetrabromide and -tetraiodide (BDH) were used without further purification. The Lewis bases employed were prepared by the reported methods⁸⁻¹⁰.

The molecular adducts were prepared by the direct interaction of the Lewis acids and bases in absolute ethanol or absolute ethanol and diethyl ether using conventional ground glass apparatus. Manipulations were carried out in a dry box flushed with nitrogen.

The melting point of the complexes were determined on the electrically operated apparatus in open capillary tubes. The values reported being uncorrected. Most of the infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded in the range 4000-250 cm^{-1} using Perkin-Elmer 521 model at the Otto Mass Chemical Laboratories, McGill University, Montreal, Canada.

Crystalline adducts were isolated by one of the following methods.

(a) In a typical experiment 2.5 m. moles of tin tetrachloride in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was mixed with 5 m. moles of the Lewis base in the same solvent (20 ml) with continuous stirring. The precipitated solid was filtered, washed with ethanol, diethylether and dried in vacuum.

(b) 2.5 m. moles of tin tetrahalide in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was mixed with a solution of

5 m. moles of the ligand in the same solvent (20 ml) and the mixture was refluxed for 2-3 hrs. The excess solvent was distilled off and the residual viscous mass was treated with excess of diethylether to precipitate the desired complex. The product was washed and dried in vacuo. The experimental results are listed in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data collected in Table 1 show that the adducts with BipyO₂ are of 1:1 stoichiometry whereas those with other amine N-oxides possess 1:2 molar ratio.

All the complexes possess high melting point and mostly decompose at their melting point. The chloride complexes are white whereas those of bromide and iodide possess pale yellow and orange colours respectively. They are non-hygroscopic except those of picoline N-oxide which are slightly moisture sensitive. The molecular weight of some of the complexes determined cryoscopically in nitromethane shows that they are monomeric in solution. Conductance measurements indicate absence of ionic species.

The absorption frequencies of diagnostic value namely NO stretching, NO bending and CH out-of-plane bending modes which are reported to be affected on complexation¹ are briefly discussed.

In the spectra of aromatic amine N-oxides examined an absorption of very strong intensity in the range 1265-1180 cm^{-1} has been assigned to NO stretching vibration mode. It undergoes a significant negative shift ($-\Delta\nu\text{NO} = 20-87 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) on complexation^{1,11,12}. The decrease in the frequency is attributed to coordination from the oxygen atom of the base causing a decrease in π -character of the N-O bond. The extent of the negative shift of this mode of vibration has been employed to determine the relative donor ability of different amine N-oxides¹³⁻¹⁵. From the collected data the relative donor ability of various amine N-oxides examined towards tin tetrahalides may be expressed as follows:

TABLE-1 ANALYTICAL DATA AND IR ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) FOR $\text{SnX}_4 \cdot n\text{L}$

X	nL	Method of Prep.	m. p. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	%Analysis		Found (calcd)		Mol. Wt. (Found) (calcd)	ν_{NO}	δ_{NO}	γ_{CH}
				Sn	C	H	N				
-	Pico	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1265vs	845s	773vs, 730vs
Cl	2PicO	a	206-8	24.40 (24.84)	30.49 (30.62)	3.21 (2.92)	4.50 (4.39)	452 (479)	1185vs 1170vs	810sh	800vs, 755vs
Br	2PicO	a	168-70	17.92 (18.11)	21.71 (21.91)	1.92 (2.13)	4.03 (4.26)	-	1180sh 1160vs	820m	800vs, 755vs
-	QO	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1230vs	885s	795vs, 766s 725m
Cl	2QO	b	286-8(d)	20.92 (21.59)	38.92 (39.20)	2.32 (2.54)	5.25 (5.10)	495 (551)	1180s 1150s	880vs	805vs, 775s 735vs
Br	2QO	b	>300	15.92 (16.32)	29.91 (29.62)	2.11 (1.92)	3.98 (3.84)	-	1185s 1155s	882vs	815vs, 770s 730vs
-	IsqO	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1182s	818s	740vs, 720vs
Cl	2IsqO	a	223-5	21.76 (21.59)	38.86 (39.21)	2.50 (2.54)	5.33 (5.10)	510 (551)	1155vs 1149vs	818s 806s	749vs, 732vs
Br	2IsqO	a	260-2	16.55 (16.32)	29.20 (29.62)	2.10 (1.92)	3.82 (3.84)	-	1151vs 1149sh	805vs	748vs, 731vs
I	2IsqO	a	130(d)	12.36 (12.90)	22.86 (23.55)	1.48 (1.55)	2.99 (3.05)	898 (917)	1150vs, br	805vs	749s, 725vs
-	BipyO ₂	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1264vs 1256vs	853s 841s	770vs, 728s
Cl	BipyO ₂	a	336-8(d)	25.99 (26.50)	27.09 (26.72)	2.05 (1.78)	6.04 (6.23)	-	1207s 1192m	840s 825s	763vs, 722s 715s
Br	BipyO ₂	a	328-30(d)	19.59 (18.97)	19.41 (19.13)	1.52 (1.27)	4.63 (4.46)	-	1202s 1190s	840s* 825s	775vs, 725s 722s
I	BipyO ₂	a	226-8(d)	15.02 (14.60)	15.12 (14.72)	0.99 (0.98)	3.54 (3.43)	-	1225vs 1215sh	848vs 833vs	772vs, 738s, 718s

The ν_{NO} vibration undergoes splitting on complexation which may be taken as an indication that the two ligand molecules occupy *cis* positions in the complexes possessing octahedral geometry.

An absorption of strong intensity in the range 900-800 cm^{-1} has been assigned to NO bending mode and from the tabulated data, it is apparent that only a slight shift of this vibration is observed on complexation^{5,11,12}, which may be attributed to two opposing effects, one similar to that of coordinated water where the bending vibration δ_{OH} is shifted towards higher frequency side and the other attributed to lowering in frequency caused by the decrease in π -character of the NO bond. As both the effects are almost equal and act in opposite direction, negligible shift in the absorption is observed.

Absorptions associated with C-H out-of-plane deformation modes are supposed to undergo slight positive shift due to tightening of the aromatic ring on complexation. A positive shift of $\sim 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been observed in this mode of vibration which is in conformity with the observations of earlier workers^{5,11,12}.

In the far IR region, there is a characteristic strong band in the range 400-300 cm^{-1} which is assigned to Sn-O stretching mode on the basis of reports on PyNO complexes of transition metals^{11,12}. The displacement of the bond to

higher frequency with increasing electronegativity of the halogen indicates a progressive increase in the Sn-O bond strength.

Tin-halogen stretching frequencies are sensitive to changes in the coordination number of the tin atom. Thus in tin tetrachloride the Sn-Cl stretching vibration appears at 403 cm^{-1} while it occurs at 332-308 cm^{-1} in all the chloro complexes reported here which is indicative of increase in coordination number of the tin atom.

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